

RESOURCES	Name/Title	Citations (Author)	Year	Abstract [max. 100 words]	URL
Comprehensive Digital Safety Framework					
EU Digital Safety Initiatives					
Overview of Key EU Institutions and Policies for Online Safety	European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA)		N/A	The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) was founded in 2004 and bolstered by the EU Cybersecurity Act. It aims to elevate cybersecurity standards across Europe. ENISA contributes to EU cyber policy, promotes trustworthy ICT products via certification schemes, collaborates with Member States and EU bodies, and aids in preparing Europe for future cyber challenges. Through knowledge sharing, capacity building, and awareness initiatives, ENISA partners with stakeholders to fortify trust in the digital economy, enhance Union infrastructure resilience, and ensure the digital security of European society and citizens.	Link
	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (EUROPOL)		N/A	Europol's mission is to support its Member States in preventing and combating all forms of serious international and organised crime, cybercrime and terrorism. Europol also works with many non-EU partner states and international organisations. The biggest security threats come from: terrorism; international drug trafficking and money laundering; organised fraud; the counterfeiting of euros; trafficking in human beings.	Link
	European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)		N/A	ECSSO was created in 2016 as the contractual counterpart to the European Commission to implement Europe's unique Public-Private Partnership in Cybersecurity – cPPP (2016-2020). Building upon the success of the cPPP, ECSSO is today the unique European cross-sectoral and independent membership organisation for cybersecurity that gathers and represents European public and private cybersecurity stakeholders and fosters their cooperation. Members of ECSSO include large companies, SMEs and start-ups, research centres, universities, end-users and operators of essential services, clusters and associations, as well as the local, regional and national public administrations across the European Union Member States and the European Free Trade Association (EFTA).	Link
	Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE)		N/A	With 57 participating States in North America, Europe and Asia, the OSCE – the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe – is the world's largest regional security organization. The OSCE works for stability, peace and democracy for more than a billion people, through political dialogue about shared values and through practical work that aims to make a lasting difference. The OSCE is a forum for political dialogue on a wide range of security issues and a platform for joint action to improve the lives of individuals and communities. The organization uses a comprehensive approach to security that encompasses the politico-military, economic and environmental, and human dimensions.	Link
Latest EU Regulations and Directives on Digital Privacy and Cybersecurity	A European strategy for a better internet for kids (BIK+)	European Commission	2022	The new strategy for a better internet for kids (BIK+), adopted on 11 May 2022, will ensure that children are protected, respected and empowered online in the new Digital Decade, in line with the European Digital Principles. An EU code on age-appropriate design, work towards standardising age assurance and verification in Europe, support for rapid assessment of illegal and harmful content, and ensuring the '116 111' number offers help to victims of cyberbullying.	Link
	European Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)	European Council	2023	The European Cyber Resilience Act is a legal framework that describes the cybersecurity requirements for hardware and software products with digital elements placed on the market of the European Union. Manufacturers are now obliged to take security seriously throughout a product's life cycle.	Link
	The EU general data protection regulation (GDPR)	European Council	2018	The EU general data protection regulation (GDPR) is the strongest privacy and security law in the world. This regulation updated and modernised the principles of the 1995 data protection directive. It was adopted in 2016 and entered into application on 25 May 2018. The GDPR lists the rights of the data subject, meaning the rights of the individuals whose personal data is being processed. The GDPR establishes the general obligations of data controllers and of those processing personal data on their behalf (processors). The regulation confirms the existing obligation for member states to establish an independent supervisory authority at national level and establishes a mechanism to create consistency in the application of data protection law across the EU.	Link
Educational Resources and Programmes					
	Online sexual coercion and extortion as a form of crime affecting	European Union Agency for	2017	Report addressing online sexual coercion and extortion as a form of crime affecting children. The report provides a law enforcement perspective of this online threat and recommends actions as a part of our preventive campaign on this topic.	Link

Curated List of EU Educational Content on Digital Safety and Literacy	Youth Internet Safety: risks and prevention	EUCPN (2018)	2018	This thematic paper is published by the EUCPN Secretariat in connection with one of the EU priorities, more specifically cybercrime. It focusses on the prevention of risks children encounter online. A brief overview is given of several forms of cybercrime considering youth and what motives and facilitating factors enhance them. The last part of the paper focusses on prevention tips with existing examples.	Link
	The European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO)	EUI Florence School of Transnational Governance	N/A	EDMO can count on a network of 14 national or multinational Hubs active across 28 countries in the EU and EEA. EDMO Hubs bring a unique potential to understand and act upon specific digital media vulnerabilities in the areas they cover. It aims to support the research community in Europe in understanding and analyzing disinformation, including providing access to data and tools for detecting misinformation campaigns.	Link
	The News Literacy Project		N/A	Offers resources and programs designed to teach students and the public how to identify credible information, recognize bias, and combat misinformation.	Link
	First Draft		2015	First Draft provides tools, training, and resources to improve skills in detecting and reporting on misinformation online.	Link
Tools for Empowerment and Protection					
Cybersecurity Tools and Resources					
Guidelines for Safe Digital Practices, Data Protection, and Empowerment	Internet Literacy Handbook of the Council of Europe	Council of Europe	2017	The Internet Literacy Handbook is a guide for teachers, parents and students which explains on getting the most out of the Internet and how to protect privacy on websites and social networks.	Link
	The EU Code of conduct on countering illegal hate speech online	European Commission	2016	To prevent and counter the spread of illegal hate speech online, in May 2016, the Commission agreed with Facebook, Microsoft, Twitter and YouTube a “Code of conduct on countering illegal hate speech online”. In the course of 2018, Instagram, Snapchat and Dailymotion took part to the Code of Conduct, Jeuxvideo.com in January 2019, TikTok in 2020 and Linked in 2021. In May and June 2022, respectively, Rakuten Viber and Twitch announced their participation to the Code of Conduct.	Link
Fact-Checking and Media Literacy					
Accredited EU Fact-Checking Platforms	EU vs Disinfo			Aims to identify and expose disinformation coming from pro-Kremlin sources, operating within the EU’s East StratCom Task Force framework.	Link
	Correctiv			A non-profit investigative newsroom in Germany that operates Correctiv.Faktencheck, focusing on debunking misinformation on social media and in public discourse.	Link
	Pagella Politica			An Italian fact-checking website that assesses the truthfulness of statements made by politicians and public figures, as well as viral claims on social media.	Link
	Les Décodeurs			A fact-checking blog by Le Monde, a leading French newspaper, dedicated to debunking myths, rumors, and misinformation circulating online and in the media.	Link
	AFP Fact Check			The fact-checking arm of the French news agency AFP, it debunks misinformation spread online globally.	Link
	<u>Maldita.es</u>			A Spanish non-profit organization focused on fact-checking and debunking false claims, particularly in the areas of science, health, and politics.	Link
Reverse Image and Video Search Tools	Snopes			One of the oldest and most well-regarded fact-checking sites, Snopes covers a wide range of topics, including urban legends, news stories, and viral content.	Link
	Google Images			Allows users to perform reverse image searches to find the source of an image or identify similar images across the web.	Link
	TinEye			A reverse image search engine that helps users find where an image came from, how it's used, or if modified versions of the image exist.	Link
	Bing Visual Search			Microsoft's search engine offers a feature for conducting reverse image searches.	Link

Browser Extensions for Fact-Checking	InVID Verification Plugin			Developed as part of a European project, this tool helps journalists verify the authenticity of images and videos from social media. A tool designed for verifying the authenticity of videos and images, particularly useful for journalists and fact-checkers.	Link	
	NewsGuard			A browser extension that provides trust ratings for news and information websites to help users distinguish between credible content and misinformation	Link	
Misinformation Tracking Tools	EU DisinfoLab			An independent non-profit organization based in Brussels that researches and tackles sophisticated disinformation campaigns targeting the EU.	Link	
	StopFake			An Ukrainian organization that works to debunk propaganda and disinformation about events in Ukraine, offering insights into tactics used in misinformation campaigns.	Link	
	Hoaxy			Visualizes the spread of claims and fact-checking online, allowing users to see how misinformation and its corrections spread on social media.	Link	
	Media Bias/Fact Check			Provides bias ratings for thousands of media sources and can be a helpful resource to assess the reliability of news providers.	Link	
Engaging Digital Learning Environments						
Catalogue of Creative and Interactive Content						
Audio-visual Educational Media: Movies, Documentaries, Cartoons, Podcasts	TV series: "Mr. Robot"		2015	"Mr. Robot" is a critically acclaimed television series created by Sam Esmail, which aired from 2015 to 2019. The show centers on Elliot Alderson, a cybersecurity engineer and hacker who struggles with social anxiety and depression. Played by Rami Malek, Elliot works for the cybersecurity firm Allsafe during the day, but at night he becomes a vigilante hacker.		
	Docu-film: "The social Dilemma"		2020	"The Social Dilemma" is a documentary-drama hybrid directed by Jeff Orlowski, released on Netflix in September 2020. The film explores the dangerous human impact of social networking, with a particular focus on how social media platforms manipulate users by using algorithms designed to keep them engaged.		
	Film: "The social Networ"		2010	This drama directed by David Fincher and written by Aaron Sorkin tells the story of the founding of Facebook and the legal battles that followed. It provides a dramatized look at the early days of social media and the ethical and personal conflicts involved.		
	Dou-film: "Terms and Conditions May Apply"		2013	It examines how companies collect, store, and use personal information from users who often overlook the terms and conditions agreements of online services.		
	Film: "Her"		2013	Directed by Spike Jonze, this film tells the story of a man who develops a romantic relationship with an intelligent operating system, exploring themes of artificial intelligence and human connection.		
	Film: "Disconnect"		2012	This film interweaves multiple stories that show how people are affected by the internet and digital communication, touching on issues like cyberbullying, identity theft, and online privacy.		
	Podcast: "IRL: Online Life is Real Life"	Mozilla			Produced by Mozilla, this podcast delves into the impact of the internet on society, covering issues like data privacy, surveillance, and the influence of algorithms. It aims to help listeners navigate the complexities of digital life.	Link
	Podcast: "Your Undivided Attention"	Center for Humane Technology			Hosted by Tristan Harris and Aza Raskin of the Center for Humane Technology, this podcast examines how technology is designed to capture our attention and the broader societal impacts of these design choices. It offers insights into how technology can be reimaged to better serve humanity.	

Recommended Books (fact-books, novels, comics) on Digital Youth Culture	Report: online sexual coercion and extortion as a form of crime affecting children / law enforcement perspective	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation	2017	Report addressing online sexual coercion and extortion as a form of crime affecting children. The report provides a law enforcement perspective of this online threat and recommends actions as a part of our preventive campaign on this topic.	Link
	THEMATIC PAPER NO. 13 - YOUTH INTERNET SAFETY: RISKS AND PREVENTION	European Crime Prevention Network	2018	A thematic paper is published by the EUCPN Secretariat in connection with one of the EU priorities, more specifically cybercrime. It focusses on the prevention of risks children encounter online. A brief overview is given of several forms of cybercrime considering youth and what motives and facilitating factors enhance them. The last part of the paper focusses on prevention tips with existing examples. Also a factsheet on Cyberbullying can be found attached.	Link
	Infographic- Top cyber threats in the EU	European Council	2022	ALL EU languages available	Link
	Book:"The Age of Surveillance Capitalism"	Shoshana Zuboff	2019	This book delves into how major tech companies exploit personal data for profit and the implications of this practice for society and democracy.	
	Novel: "1984"	George Orwell		This classic dystopian novel explores themes of surveillance, government control, and the loss of individual privacy, which resonate strongly with concerns about modern digital surveillance.	
	Book: "Digital Minimalism: Choosing a Focused Life in a Noisy World"	Cal Newport	2019	This book advocates for a more intentional and focused approach to technology use, providing strategies for minimizing digital distractions and improving quality of life.	
	Fiction-Novel: "Super Sad True Love Story"	Gary Shteyngart	2010	A satirical novel set in a near-future dystopian America where people's worth is determined by their social media presence and credit scores, highlighting the absurdities and dangers of a hyperconnected world.	
Games (online/offline)	AR-in-a-Box Game	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)		AR-in-a-Box is a comprehensive solution for cybersecurity awareness activities designed to meet the needs of public bodies, operators of essential services, and both large and small private companies. It provides theoretical and practical knowledge on how to design and implement effective cybersecurity awareness programmes,	Link
	<u>Google Interland</u>	Google		Google Interland, part of Google's Be Cool on the Internet initiative, is primarily intended for children. The experience is divided into four adventures that introduce fundamental cybersecurity concepts in a simple and intuitive manner. Its primary goal is to empower participants, especially young ones, to avoid online traps, recognize safe behavior on social media platforms, manage passwords effectively, recognize bullies and predators, and understand responsible data sharing. The game features various levels and challenges, requiring players to answer essential questions while providing hands-on opportunities to apply their newfound knowledge.	Link
	RISE	Erasmus Project		A modern and innovative smartphone Game (and an online version) for young people, to improve their digital skills and support them to identify, prevent and mitigate risks of online social networks. This Game will enhance online vigilance of young people, and offer them resources and tools to deal with underlying OSN threats.	Link
	Cyber Survival Game	ATED, Ticino Association for Digital Evolution		Cyber Survival Game is a board game that aims to spread the culture of cyber security among the general public. It is aimed at both adults and children from the age of 8 and aims to raise awareness of the main cyber threats in the home, schools and companies using a playful and engaging approach.	Link
Support and Advisory Networks					

Helplines and Support Services					
Directory of Helplines for Immediate Assistance and Support Services for Digital Well-being	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol)		2022	Europol's mission is to support its Member States in preventing and combating all forms of serious international and organised crime, cybercrime and terrorism. Europol also works with many non-EU partner states and international organisations. Europol is a high-security operational centre that operates non-stop: 24 hours a day, seven days a week. It contain links to contact helplines in the EU countries.	Link
Community and Peer Support Networks					
Initiatives Promoting Peer Mentorship and Leadership in Digital Safety	European Cyber Security Month (ECSM)	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) and the European Commission		The European Cybersecurity Month (ECSM) is an annual campaign in October to raise awareness about cybersecurity threats and promote best practices. it features various activities and resources to educate the public and enhance digital security. Key themes include cyber hygiene and cyber skills, emphasizing the importance of being cautious online with the motto "Think Before U Click."	Link
	The International Day against Violence and Bullying at School, including Cyberbullying	UNESCO		The International Day against Violence and Bullying at School, including Cyberbullying, is observed on the first Thursday of November. Initiated by UNESCO, it aims to raise awareness about the negative impact of school violence on children's education, health, and well-being.	Link
	Safer Internet Day	European Commission		Safer Internet Day (SID) is an annual event that promotes the safe and positive use of digital technology for children and young people. Celebrated in over 180 countries, it involves various stakeholders including schools, parents, governments, and industry leaders, all working together to create a safer online environment.	Link
Platforms for Community Engagement and Sharing Best Practices	European Anti-Bullying Network (EAN)			The European Anti-bullying Network is an international non-profit-making association, created in 2013 in the framework of the EU-funded project "European Anti-bullying Network", and officially registered in Belgium in 2015. EAN is an active network of organizations working in and across Europe to combat bullying and school violence. The platform provide resources and shared best practices from EU countries.	Link
	The European Cybersecurity Challenge	The European Cybersecurity Agency		The European Cybersecurity Challenge is the annual cybersecurity championship during which teams of 10 members aged 14 to 24, representing European and some invited non-European countries, participate on-site in cybersecurity competitions (CTF - Capture The Flag) over 2 days, to determine the European champion	Link
EU projects \\\ Inter-project synergies					
Insights from EU Projects and Research					
	CyberYouth			Cyberyouth is a EU project focused on understanding how cybersecurity and skills are perceived by youth organisations. In the first part of the project, we have investigated on the status of cybersecurity awareness and capacity of youth organisations in Italy, Bulgaria, Spain, The Netherlands, Estonia and Turkey.	Link
	Cooperation to Combat Cyber-bullying and Hate Speech in (Pre-)Primary Schools	VSI EDUKACINIAI PROJEKTAI	2020	EU funded project focused on the challenges of the digital world – cyberbullying and hate speech online – and proposes a different approach of work – listening to the opinion of children and promoting co-education where schools as well as parents are involved in solving these issues.	Link

Case Studies and Success Stories from other EU-Funded Projects	A Safer School, a Friendlier School	Colegiul National de Informatica Grigore Moisil	2020	EU funded project focused to increase the number of teachers qualified to prevent and intervene in bullying situations, with the aim of increasing the degree of comfort and safety that students feel when they come to school. A safer school becomes a friendlier school for students, and the consequence is that they will be absent less.	Link
	Digital Competence and eSafety Save this project in my Booklet	2nd Lyceum of Kos	2020	This project, aims towards the development of digital literacy and eSafety skills, achieving a high degree of DC, developing an e-safety policy, supporting innovative/open pedagogies in education (Virtual LC, ICT tools, Google Classroom, Wikis, Collaborative/Peer Learning).	Link
	BUILDING REAL AND VIRTUAL BRIDGES	Istituto Istruzione Superiore Statale Italo Calvino Rozzano	2020	A School Exchange Partnerships intended to create a connection among different groups from different countries, both in a real and virtual world. Its aim was to go beyond frontiers, remove obstacles in order to reach effective communication, and promote a constructive sharing of ideas among teachers and students.	Link
Tailored Content for Diverse Audiences					
For SCHOOLS: Educators and Trainers					
Specialized Resources and Training for Incorporating Digital Safety in Curriculums (Technical and Social Threats)	eSafety Label	European Schoolnet		eSafety Label is a Europe-wide accreditation and support service for schools, aiming to provide a secure and enriching environment, for safe access to online technology as part of the teaching and learning experience.	Link
	ISACA			As a globally recognized leader in IS/IT for over 50 years, ISACA is a professional membership organization committed to the advancement of digital trust by empowering IS/IT professionals to grow their skills and knowledge in audit, cybersecurity, emerging tech and more.	Link
	Cybersecurity: how the EU tackles cyber threats	European Council		Cybersecurity: how the EU tackles cyber threats	Link
	ENISA Threat Landscape 2022	The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)		An annual report on the status of the cybersecurity threat landscape. It identifies the top threats, major trends observed with respect to threats, threat actors and attack techniques, as well as impact and motivation analysis. It also describes relevant mitigation measures.	Link
	Coursera certificate			Get on the fast track to a career in cybersecurity. In this certificate program, you'll learn in-demand skills at your own pace, no degree or experience required.	Link
	Family Online Safety Institute (FOSI)			The Family Online Safety Institute brings a unique, international perspective to the potential risks, harms as well as the rewards of our online lives. FOSI's 30+ members are among the leading telecommunications, social media, cybersecurity, gaming and internet companies in the world. Our work encompasses public policy, industry best practices, and good digital parenting.	Link
For FAMILIES: Parents and Guardians					

Strategies and Guides on Navigating Digital Parenting Challenges	The Cyber Threat Landscape: Understanding and Mitigating Risks.	Evren, R., & Milson, S. (2024). The Cyber Threat Landscape: Understanding and Mitigating Risks.	2024	emphasizes the significance of proactive measures, such as security awareness training and collaboration between public and private sectors, in building a resilient defense against cyber threats. By fostering a deeper understanding of the cyber threat landscape and advocating for a proactive and adaptive cybersecurity approach, this paper aims to empower stakeholders to fortify their defenses and mitigate the potential impact of cyber risks in an everevolving digital environment.	Link
	Cyber Security Threats and Counter Measures in Digital Age	Thakur, M. (2024). Cyber Security Threats and Countermeasures in Digital Age. Journal of Applied Science and Education (JASE)	2024	This study offers detailed analysis of the cyber threat environment in the digital era along with suggestions for doable protective measures. The report outlines a number of cyber threats, including malware, phishing scams, ransomware, and insider threats. It looks at the continually evolving tactics employed by cybercriminals, such as social engineering, zero-day flaws, and sophisticated persistent threats. The growing hazards associated with cutting-edge technology, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and artificial intelligence, are also examined. The importance of a multi-layered security strategy to counter these attacks is emphasized in the article.	
	The EU Strategy on the Rights of the Child and the European Child Guarantee	European Commission	2021	The new comprehensive EU Strategy on the Rights of the Child and the European Child Guarantee are major policy initiatives put forward by the European Commission to better protect all children, to help them fulfil their rights and to place them right at the centre of EU policy making.	Link
	Family Online Safety Institute (FOSI)			The Family Online Safety Institute brings a unique, international perspective to the potential risks, harms as well as the rewards of our online lives. FOSI's 30+ members are among the leading telecommunications, social media, cybersecurity, gaming and internet companies in the world. Our work encompasses public policy, industry best practices, and good digital parenting.	Link
For CYBER-NATIVES: Youth and Students					
Interactive Guides, Toolkits, Blogs Tailored for Young Digital Users	The European Union's plan for children's rights-	European Commission	2021	This is the EU Strategy on Children's Rights (The Plan) in an easy-to-read version. It has been produced in partnership with children. Two groups of children and young people from two schools in Dublin, Ireland, were brought together by the Centre for Children's Rights at Queen's University in Belfast, Northern Ireland. They worked together to decide how the key messages of 'The Plan' should be explained to children in this booklet.	Link
	EUROPOLE- How to set your privacy settings on social media	EUROPOLE		EUROPOLE- How to set your privacy settings on social media	Link
	EUROPOLE-Removing links to explicit content	EUROPOLE		EUROPOLE-Removing links to explicit content	Link
	European Youth Portal- Be safe online!	European Youth Portal		European Youth Portal-Be safe online!	Link

	Infographic- Towards a digital Europe	Council of the European Union		Infographic- Towards a digital Europe	Link
	Feature Story- Your life online: how is the EU making it easier and safer for you?	Council of the European Union		Feature Story- Your life online: how is the EU making it easier and safer for you?	Link